

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding method

Genetic studies of aroma in the elite cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) aromatic japonica line Shangbai A

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Medium-maturing Shangbai A possesses the male sterile cytoplasm of cultivar Chinsurah Boro II.

To study aroma inheritance, we crossed CMS line Shangbai A and its maintainer, Shangbai B, in 1989 with three nonaromatic restorer lines to obtain four crosses. In 1990, we backcrossed three of the F_1 with the CMS line used as maternal parent.

P_1, P_2, F_1, F_2 , and BC_1 progeny from the four crosses were sown in May 1991. Aroma from single plants was evaluated after 45 d. Leaf blades (2 g/plant) from each progeny were soaked in 10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution for 10 min at 25-30 °C. Panelists classified the samples as aromatic or nonaromatic by smelling the contents of the test tubes.

Expressions of aroma in leaf blade and grain were similar in Shangbai A and Shangbai B (Table 1). This implied that classifying aromatic/nonaromatic grains on the basis of leaf samples would be reliable.

F_1 plants from all the crosses were nonaromatic, indicating that aroma in Shangbai A (Shangbai B) was recessive (Table 2). Segregating ratios of nonaromatic to aromatic plants in BC_1 and F_2 were 1:1 and 3:1, respectively.

F_2 segregation behavior of Shangbai A/Zhi 7 and Shangbai B/Zhi 7 was identical. This indicates that the cytoplasm from Chinsurah Boro II did not affect expression of aroma in Shangbai A. Results showed that a recessive nuclear gene controls aroma in Shangbai A. □

Table 1. Percent accuracy for aromatic identification of 2-g leaf blade and grain samples and individual grain in Shangbai A and Shangbai B.

	Shangbai A		Shangbai B	
	Samples (no.)	Accuracy (%)	Samples (no.)	Accuracy (%)
2-g leaf blade ^a	30	100	19	100
2-g grain ^a	49	95.5	57	97.3
Individual grain ^b	83	84.4	73	90.4

^aTwo-gram samples were evaluated for aroma in 10 ml 1.7% KOH. ^bIndividual grains were evaluated in 5 ml 1.7% KOH.

Table 2. Behavior of parents (CMS, maintainers, and restorers), F_1 , BC_1 , and F_2 with regard to aroma.

Designation	Plants (no.)			Ratio of nonaromatic to aromatic		χ^2	P
	Tested	Nonaromatic	Aromatic	Actual	Expected		
Parent							
Shangbai A	30	0	30	0:1	0:1		
Shangbai B	19	0	19	0:1	0:1		
Zhi 7	21	21	0	1:0	1:0		
90-11	20	20	0	1:0	1:0		
4144	22	22	0	1:0	1:0		
F_1							
Shangbai A/Zhi 7	21	21	0	1:0	1:0		
Shangbai A/90-11	25	25	0	1:0	1:0		
Shangbai A/4144	23	23	0	1:0	1:0		
Shangbai B/Zhi 7	31	31	0	1:0	1:0		
BC_1							
Shangbai A/Shangbai A/Zhi 7	92	47	45	1:1.04	1:1	0.044	0.75-0.90
Shangbai A/Shangbai A/90-11	84	43	41	1:1.05	1:1	0.047	0.75-0.90
Shangbai A/Shangbai A/4144	101	49	52	0.94:1	1:1	0.089	0.75-0.90
Total	277	139	138	1.01:1	1:1	0.003	>0.90
F_2							
Shangbai A/Zhi 7	123	94	29	3.24:1	3:1	0.13	0.50-0.75
Shangbai A/90-11	160	115	45	2.55:1	3:1	0.77	0.25-0.50
Shangbai A/4144	158	119	39	3.05:1	3:1	0.01	>0.90
Shangbai B/Zhi 7	141	106	35	3.02:1	3:1	0.02	>0.90
Total	582	434	148	2.93:1	3:1	0.057	0.75-0.90

Effect of paper bags used to cover hand-crossed panicles on seed set and vigor

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White-colored glassine bags are usually used in hand-crossing rice panicles. We compared the effect of six types of paper bags on seed set and vigor of F_1 seeds in the MORIF greenhouse from Dec 1990 to Mar 1991 (see table).

The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design with four

replications. IR48 was the female parent and IR42 the male. A vacuum emasculator was used. Hybrid seeds were harvested (100 from each replication) and sown.

Panicles covered with brown bread paper after pollination produced heavier seeds than panicles covered with white glassine bags (see table). One hundred seeds weighed 2.24 g for the brown bread paper, significantly more than the 1.5 g for the white glassine bag. Higher seed germination and seedling growth accompanied greater seed size. Bag type did not influence seed set percentage.

We determined the transmittance value of different bags with a DV-7

spectrophotometer. The range covered the ultraviolet (UV), visible, and near-infrared spectrum. The transmittance of whole wavelength range was lowest in both white and brown bread paper bags.

Reduced UV and visible radiation transmittance through the bread paper

bags may minimize photoreceptor activation in the seeds and divert some of the storage carbohydrate to the shikimic process. This would result in heavier seeds for the bread paper-covered panicles than for the glassine-covered panicles □

Effect of type of paper bag used to cover hand-crossed panicles on percentage of seed setting, weight of F₁ seed, seed germination, and hybrid vigor components.^a MORIF, Ujung Pandang, Indonesia, 1991.

Bags used	Seed set percentage (%)	100-seed wt (g)	Seed germination (%)	Seedling plant ht (cm)	Root length (cm)	Dry matter of seedlings (g/5 plants)	Light transmittance (%)	
							250 nm	850 nm
White glassine	24.01	1.5409 c	65.50 b	29.30 b	14.50 bc	0.7103 bc	5.7	23.5
Yellow glassine	32.33	1.3988 c	57.00 bc	29.23 bc	14.67 bc	0.6474 cd	6.0	27.2
Green glassine	27.10	1.5290 c	47.50 cd	26.37 c	13.75 c	0.6961 bcd	0.8	14.2
Red glassine	29.12	1.5151 c	40.25 d	23.47 c	13.92 c	0.6307 d	3.0	38.8
White bread paper	29.83	1.9846 b	64.50 b	30.03 b	15.25 b	0.7598 b	0.6	1.2
Brown bread paper	27.20	2.2427 a	82.00 a	37.33 a	20.75 a	1.0467 d	0.1	3.4
CV (%)	12.5	12.6	10.8	14.2	16.2	11.6		

^a In each column, treatment means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at P = 0.05.

Performance of IRRI rice hybrids in Mandya, Karnataka, India

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Six hybrids using CMS lines IR62829 A and IR58025 A were evaluated against local checks Jaya, IR36, and Rasi at the Regional Research Station, Mandya. Seedlings (26 d old) were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing on 4 Aug 1990 in

5.9-m² plots laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

The IR58025 A combinations outperformed the IR62829 A hybrids and local checks (see table). Jaya yielded more than the IR62829 A hybrids.

IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R matured in 117 d and IR58025 A/IR35366-62-1-2-3 R in 124 d. These hybrids had 25% more standard heterosis than IR36, the comparable check, for days to maturity, and 10% more than Jaya. IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3 R recorded higher yield, but duration was 136 d. □

Performance of IRRI hybrids in Mandya, Karnataka, India.

Hybrid and check	Maturity duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Sterile plants (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) in heterosis over			
								Jaya	IR36	Rasi	
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	117	78.2	318	141	10.9	3.9	7.6	10.6	26.2	24.4	
IR62829 A/IR9761-19-1 R	120	70.2	428	125	18.2	5.0	4.7	-31.9	-22.3	-23.5	
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3 R	136	88.7	422	143	20.4	0	7.6	10.6	26.2	24.4	
IR62829 A/IR29723-143-3 R	126	73.9	317	162	36.3	6.2	6.2	-9.0	3.4	-2.3	
IR62829 A/IR10198-66-2 R	120	78.6	361	137	5.9	7.6	6.5	-4.9	-8.5	-6.9	
IR58025 A/IR35366-62-1-2-3 R	124	80.4	407	172	33.9	6.1	7.7	12.7	28.5	26.7	
Jaya	141	100.8	336	155	19.6	0	6.8				
IR36	127	68.4	339	125	20.5	0	6.0				
Rasi	124	85.6	348	127	4.3	0	6.0				
LSD							1.4				
CV (%)							13.1				

Grain quality

Effect of growth location on rice protein content and composition

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Grain samples of rice cultivar L202 from different locations had varied cooking quality. We studied the effect of growth location on the stability of rice protein content and composition.

L202 seeds from the 1989 harvests in California, USA, and Seville, Spain, were grown in 1990 in Italy.

The protein content of brown rice from Italian crops was lower than that of American and Spanish samples (see table). Quantitative and qualitative differences existed among the four

AL-PAGE patterns of acetic extracts of brown rice from rice cultivar L202 grown in different locations: I = California (Californian seed), II = Italy (Californian seed), III = Spain (Spanish seed), and IV = Italy (Spanish seed).